

Report on iNEXT-Discovery Covid-19 research

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[iNEXT-Discovery](#) is the EC-funded Horizon2020 project integrating networking, access and joint research activities for structural biology ([Grant Agreement #871037](#)), coordinated by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI). As part of this project, during the Corona-pandemic Covid-related facility access for external users has been fast-tracked, both through our continuous access portals and via a shared call for proposals with [Instruct-ERIC](#). For optimizing these focused research activities, we closely worked together with the [Covid19-NMR](#) consortium, led by the high-field NMR group in Frankfurt am Main (Partner GUF in iNEXT-Discovery).

Since February 2020, iNEXT-Discovery received a total of 30 Covid-19 research applications, of which 29 were approved and 20 reported access to one of our facilities. Several of these user access projects, besides studies from our consortium partners, publish and discuss structures of SARS-CoV-2 proteins, RNA and other molecules, as well as their interactions. Next to these (see Table below), additional iNEXT-Discovery output report on applications and technological developments that are likely also of relevance to study details of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and treatment of Covid.

Of the - thus far - 18 Open Access iNEXT-Discovery publications that refer to Covid-19, Corona or SARS, most come from activities with the global Covid19-NMR consortium (c.f. PubID 126). At least three publications that focused on Corona (PubIDs 25, 93 and 151) can be directly related to user facility access. More publications are expected to emerge after the project and its access services come to an end on July 31, 2024.

Publ D	TITLEc	DOI	Groups
6	Multitarget Virtual Screening for Drug Repurposing in COVID19	10.26434/chemrxiv.12652997.v2	CSIC
21	Magnetization transfer to enhance NOE cross-peaks among labile protons: Applications to imino-imino sequential walks in SARS-CoV-2-derived RNAs	10.1002/anie.202015948	GUF
25	¹ H, ¹³ C, and ¹⁵ N backbone chemical-shift assignments of SARS-CoV-2 non-structural protein 1 (leader protein)	10.1007/s12104-021-10019-6	GUF (PID 16049)
26	3D Heteronuclear Magnetization Transfers for the Establishment of Secondary Structures in SARS-CoV-2-Derived RNAs	10.1021/jacs.1c01914	GUF
29	Large-Scale Recombinant Production of the SARS-CoV-2 Proteome for High-Throughput and Structural Biology Applications	10.3389/fmolb.2021.653148	GUF / CIRMMP
44	Secondary structure determination of conserved SARS-CoV-2 RNA elements by NMR spectroscopy	10.1093/nar/gkaa1013	GUF
45	Exploring the druggability of conserved RNA regulatory elements in the SARS-CoV-2 genome	10.1002/anie.202103693	GUF
47	SARS-CoV-2 Mpro inhibition by a zinc ion: structural features and hints for drug design	10.1039/d1cc02956h	CIRMMP
72	Secretory IgA and T cells targeting SARS-CoV-2 spike protein are transferred to the breastmilk upon mRNA vaccination	10.1016/j.xcrm.2021.100468	ITQB (NA)
90	The Extended Hadamard Transform: Sensitivity-Enhanced NMR Experiments Among Labile and Non-Labile ¹ Hs of SARS-CoV-2-derived RNAs	10.1002/cphc.202100704	GUF
93	Binding adaptation of GS-441524 diversifies macro domains and downregulate SARS-CoV-2 de-MARylation capacity	10.1016/j.jmb.2022.167720	GUF (PID 12863)
99	Comprehensive Fragment Screening of the SARS-CoV-2 Proteome Explores Novel Chemical Space for Drug Development	10.1002/anie.202205858	GUF / CIRMMP
105	Rational design of the zonulin inhibitor AT1001 derivatives as potential anti SARSCoV-2	10.1016/j.ejmech.2022.114857	EMBL-GR
126	The COVID19-NMR Consortium: A Public Report on the Impact of this New Global Collaboration	10.1002/ange.202217171	GUF (NA)
151	Blood pH Analysis in Combination with Molecular Medical Tools in Relation to COVID-19 Symptoms	10.3390/biomedicines11051421	UU (PID 13551)
172	High-resolution structure of stem-loop 4 from the 5'-UTR of SARS-CoV-2 solved by solution state NMR	10.1093/nar/gkad762	GUF
191	Targeting the Main Protease (Mpro, nsp5) by Growth of Fragment Scaffolds Exploiting Structure-Based Methodologies	10.1021/acscchembio.3c00720	GUF / NKI / CIRMMP / HZB
204	NMR characterization and ligand binding site of the stem loop 2 motif (s2m) from the Delta variant of SARS-CoV-2	10.1261/rna.079902.123	GUF